

Research Article

Correlates of Performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers in Calabanga Community College

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Abstract: The quality of education offered by any institution is often determined by the performance of graduates it produces. This study was conducted to determine the predictors of performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) as the bases for a contextualized intervention program. A total of 117 graduates from batch 2016 to 2019 of Bachelor of Secondary Education graduates of Calabanga Community College were the respondents of this study. This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design utilizing a survey questionnaire and documentary analysis for data gathering. Data were treated using descriptive statistics, chi-square test of independence, and Pearson's Product Moment of Correlation. The profile showed that 70% of the respondents were in the 19 to 25 age bracket, three-fourths were female, and almost all were single. The majority of respondents had a monthly income of 5,000 to 10,000 pesos. On average, their grade performance in high school was 85%, and in the college entrance examination, the most significant percentage got 86-90%. As to their College GWA, generally, their grades ranged between 1.51 and 2.0. The BSED graduates' General Education performance consistently recorded the highest means of 82.30, 80.53, 81.08, and 82.21, respectively, from 2016-2019. On the other hand, their performance in major courses was better than in their professional education courses in the two successive periods, 2016 and 2017, except in the 2018 and 2019 examinations. Their LET performance was highly affected by teacher factors (3.61) and least affected by the family factor (2.57). Their performance along specialization and professional education is significantly associated with their college academic performance, whereas their performance in General Education, with their high school academic performance. Among the factors considered, the general and professional education performance was positively and significantly predicted by personal factors.

Keywords: Tracer Study, Licensure Examination Performance, Calabanga Community College.

Introduction

The Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is a significant necessity to qualify the passage into the field of the teaching profession. The LET is a written assessment required for all professional teacher applicants as mandated by the Republic Act (RA) 7836, also known as the Teacher Professionalization Act of 1994. Hence, to become a qualified, professional, and licensed teacher, one should pass the LET administered by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) governed by Republic Act 8981, also known as the PRC Modernization Act of 2000 (Norman, 2018). The Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) is mandated to administer, implements, and enforces the regulatory laws and policies of the country concerning the regulation and licensing of the various professional and occupations under its jurisdiction, including the enhancement and maintenance of professional and occupational standards and ethics and the enforcement to the rules and regulations relative thereto (RA 8981). Also, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) issued a Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 30 series of 2004 entitled "Revised Policies and Standards for

Undergraduate Teacher Education Curriculum” The Order particularly sets, among others, the following: program specification, competency standards, curriculum, and course specifications. The quality of education by schools in the country is being gauged based on the performance of graduates in the licensure examination for board courses like the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) which is known as the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).

In this sense, licensure examination is considered one factor that influences the quality of teachers and teaching in the country; thus, average passing performance in LET is one of the outcome indicators under the present curriculum and in the instruction parameters. LET ensures and defines the competence of graduates to teach in the teaching field. The crucial step before they receive the license is to serve as the identity of being professional teachers fitted for the profession.

Accordingly, the ultimate goal of every Teacher Education Institution (TEI) is for their students to achieve high performance, if not 100% passing rate, in taking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Hence, it requires all the necessary preparations for what the school can provide and the examinees’ personal accountability. These desires are attuned to the notion that licensure examination provides quality assurance of education, promotes professionalism among teachers, and somewhat improves student outcomes (Bagadion and Tullao, 2018). Passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) indicates quality education.

To achieve such a perspective, one of UNESCO’s agenda for 2030 along Sustainable Development Goals is the Education for Sustainable Development. UNESCO’s Action framework ensures inclusive and equitable quality education and promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all. In UNESCO’s target of indicative strategies, by 2030, it will provide equal access for all men and women to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university (Manhas, 2022). In the Philippines, the 1987 constitution guarantees and protects the right to education of all citizens by ensuring that institutions of learning promote access, equity, quality, and relevance even as they exercise their institutional academic freedom. Article XIV, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution provides that: The state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all (Philippines, 2018).

As a Teacher Education Institution and a local college in Bicol Region since 2002, Calabanga Community College gauged its performance by looking into the LET results from the PRC as a regulatory agency. The record of the LET Performance for the past five years, Calabanga Community College, obtained the following passing percentages for its first takers during September examinations such as; 48.15%, 62.96%, 67.53%, 45.45% and 66.7% respectively for the school years 2016 to 2021. While the overall performances are 40.63%, 46.15%, 63.83%, 36.25% and 66.7% respectively.

The main reason for the study was to determine the correlates of Bachelor of Secondary Education graduates of Calabanga Community College (CCC) from 2016 to 2019 to their Licensure Examination. The study was supported by several relevant theories, such as: Dewey’s curriculum theory (1902), which stated that the curriculum should ultimately produce students who would deal effectively with the modern world; the theory of Simmons (2015), known as the Performance Management Theory of Action, which emphasizes the importance of teachers in studying for an institution, and states that the teacher’s educational background was the basis for the learner’s achievement in academic and curricular activities for the identification of an effective school along with the students; and lastly, the theory of attribution developed by Weiner which avers that students’ failures and successes are attributed in terms of the abilities, efforts, lacks, and difficulty of the learning task. This would help school officials, curriculum makers, parents, teachers, and students. The findings of this study could serve as: guide in the development planning of school administrators, programs, and department heads for continuous improvement of the quality of

instruction; bases for the innovations, revisions, and improvement of the existing curriculum among curriculum makers; motivation for parents to help and understand the situation of students by appreciating their complex works; valuable source of information among instructors in designing and implementing plans and programs to enhance and improve the implementation of the curriculum by adopting and adapting contextualized activities and intervention programs; and, basis and preparation for students in the teaching profession, particularly in taking the licensure examination.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive-correlational research design utilizing survey and documentary analysis. The respondents of this study were the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in Biological Science graduates of Calabanga Community College (CCC) from Academic Year 2015-2016 to 2018-2019. The total retrieved questionnaires from Batch 2016 were 21; in 2017, 19; in 2018, 38; and in 2019, 39. In sum, the total frequency of the retrieved questionnaires was 117. The study utilized a self-developed questionnaire which was crafted through item pooling. The names, addresses, and contact numbers of the graduates were obtained from the registrar for the facility of trailing. The researcher administered some of the questionnaires using electronic mail or e-mail or Facebook messengers, for most of the graduate respondents use computers in their places, offices or companies. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and collect data in frequency and percent distribution tables. Inferential statistics such as Chi-Square and Pearson’s Product Moment of Correlation were also utilized to examine the statistical relationships and associations of variables. To define the content validity of the questionnaires, the researcher consulted experts in instrument development. Their suggestions and recommendations were noted and integrated into the final form. The questionnaire was pretested with sampled population or graduates of other courses in the other schools. Thereafter, the results were subjected to reliability testing.

Results and Discussion

Demographics: Information about the respondents was subdivided into personal, home, and academic characteristics. These include age, sex, civil status, monthly family income, high school academic grade, college entrance examination, and college academic standing (Table 1). Results indicated that most (82 out of 117) graduates who took the Licensure Examination for Teachers were 19-25 years old. The eldest among them was 39 years old on the actual day of the examination. In terms of sex distribution, about 75% were female. Only 25.6% were male. Regarding civil status, 90 out of 117 were single, and 27 were married. Of their monthly income, the largest percentages were in the income bracket between P5,000 to P10,000 pesos and below 5,000.00 on average.

Table 1. Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) graduates’ academic and personal profile

Attributes	Categories	N = 117	Percentage
Age	33-39	12	10.3
	26-32	23	19.7
	19-25	82	70.1
Sex	Male	30	25.6
	Female	87	74.4
Civil Status	Single	90	76.9
	Married	27	23.1
Monthly Family Income	Above 25,000.00	10	8.5
	20,001-25,000.00	14	12.0
	15,001-20,000.00	12	10.3
	10,001-15,000.00	18	15.4
	5,001-10,000.00	35	29.9
	Below 5,000.00	28	23.9
High School Academic Performance (GA)	Above 90%	10	8.5
	86%-90%	27	23.1

	85% and below	80	68.4
College Entrance Test (CET) Results	91% and above	10	8.5
	86-90%	51	43.6
	81-85 %	44	37.6
	76-80%	10	8.5
	75 Below	2	1.7
College Academic Performance (GWA)	2.01-2.3	1	0.9
	1.71-2.00	58	49.6
	1.51-1.70	44	37.6
	1.20-1.50	14	12.0

As to their high school academic performance, 68.4 percent had 85% and below General Weighted Average (GWA). In college exam results, around 44 percent obtained grades between 86-90%, and their GWA was between 1.71-2.00.

Results indicated that when the respondents took the LET examination, they were just at the right age, female-dominated, single, with income below 5,000 monthly. They also have good academic standing in high school and college and obtained satisfactory performance in the college entrance test results. It can also be added that with the given family income, it can be inferred that more than half of the respondents belonged to low-income families or at the poverty threshold, considering that their monthly payment is only P5,000 pesos and below.

The results and findings of this study were similar to the findings of Rudio (2016) and Angeles (2019), which revealed that the majority of examinees were female. The studies of the foregoing researchers also disclosed that LET performance had no significant relationship with age. Moreover, studies conducted by Chan-Rabanal and Susan L. Manzano, 2018 and Foronda (2017) revealed that the personal profile of the graduates correlates significantly with their LET performance. Hence, this finding supports the present study on predictors of performance in the licensure examination.

Licensure Examination Performance: Table 2 presents the performance of Bachelor of Secondary Education graduates in the Licensure Examination for Teachers from 2016 to 2019. It can be gleaned from the results that in the LET Examination from 2016 to 2019, the highest mean performance of graduates was consistently in General Educational courses. It had 82.30 in 2016, 80.53 in 2017, 80.01 in 2018, and 82.21 in 2019. The lowest, however, was in Professional Education courses in 2016 (76.42) and 2017 (77.68) and major courses in 2018 (76.35) and 2019 (74.67). Of these results, the highest standard deviation values were noted in 2018 in the three subject areas with 10.880, 9.386, and 10.529, respectively, for General Education Courses, Professional Education Courses, and Major Courses. This suggests the heterogeneity of the results in this specified year. These findings can then deduce that their LET performance was spread out or highly dispersed. The results in 2016, nevertheless, were instead showing the opposite. It had the lowest SD values of 3.600, 2.962, and 3.376 steadily in those areas. It then implies that the performance of graduates this year was almost the same or homogenous.

Overall, only in General Education Courses did the graduates obtain an average performance level. The two other areas, Professional Education Courses and Major Courses, only achieved below-average levels. The sum of all their scores was 78.67 (below average), with an SD of 6.247. The preceding findings were consistent with the study of Lucido (2016). In his study, the passing percentages and mean scores for secondary level in the general education, professional education, and specialization, the three tests for the secondary teachers' group show that secondary group examinees performed better in general education (mean-50.12%) than in professional education (mean-48.05%). Among the ten specializations, the specialists in Biological Science got the highest percentage (68.10%) and the highest mean (54.90%).

Table 2. Licensure Examination Performance of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) Graduates: CY 2016-19

Year	Courses	Std. Deviation	Mean	Descriptive Rating
2016	General Education Courses	3.600	82.30	Average
	Professional Education Courses	2.962	76.42	Below Average
	Major Courses	3.376	77.85	Below Average
	Total	3.312	78.86	Below Average
2017	General Education Courses	5.420	80.53	Average
	Professional Education Courses	5.677	77.68	Below Average
	Major Courses	4.001	78.68	Below Average
	Total	5.033	78.96	Below Average
2018	General Education Courses	10.880	81.08	Average
	Professional Education Courses	9.386	77.72	Below Average
	Major Courses	10.529	76.35	Below Average
	Total	10.265	78.38	Below Average
2019	General Education Courses	6.530	82.21	Average
	Professional Education Courses	6.512	78.62	Below Average
	Major Courses	6.093	74.67	Below Average
	Total	6.378	78.50	Below Average
Overall Total		6.247	78.67	Below Average
Legend: 95-100-Excellent; 90-94-Superior; 85-89-Above Average; 80-84-Average; 75-79-Below Average; Below 74-Poor/Failed				

Perceived factors affecting Licensure Examination Performance: The summary of the perceived factors (i.e., teacher, school, personal, and family aspects and review strategies) affecting the performance of BSEd graduates in the licensure examination is shown in Table 3. As indicated, the teacher factor was perceived to have predominantly affected students' LET performance; this is least affected, on the other hand, by the family factors. They were evidenced by the mean ratings of 3.61 and 2.56 for the teacher and family factors, respectively. These findings imply that graduates perceive their teachers as among the critical factors in their LET achievements. This could also suggest some positive attributes among their teachers that can be vital in improving students' LET performance, such as teachers' competence, teaching strategies, enabling, and engaging qualities appropriate to students' needs.

These results and findings were supported by the studies of Faltado (2014) and Visco (2015), which disclosed that teachers' competence as a result of educational attainment and training attended greatly influence the performance of graduates in the Licensure Examinations.

Table 3. Perceived factors affecting Licensure Examination Performance of BSEd graduates

Parameters	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher Aspect	3.61	Always
Review Preparations	2.92	Often
School Aspect	2.86	Often
Personal Aspect	2.86	Often
Family Aspect	2.57	Often
Mean	2.96	Often
Legend: 3.26-4.00 Always; 2.51-3.25 Often; 1.76-2.50-Sometimes; 1.00-1.75 Never		

In addition, the study of Chan-Rabanal and Susan L. Manzano, (2018) was consistent with this study's findings. The personal profile of the graduates in his study was found to correlate significantly with their LET performance. Furthermore, the Performance theory of Schechner (as cited by Elger, 1985) also affirms the result of the present study. The idea believes that the current level of performance depends holistically on six components: context, level of knowledge, skills, level of identity, personal factors, and fixed factors. Some other factors, like their review preparations (2.92), school aspect (2.86), and personal aspect (2.86), have also been viewed by the graduates as often affecting their performance.

Demographics and Licensure Examination Performance: Table 4 shows the association between personal demographic profile and the LET performance of graduates. It could be gleaned from the results that most of the attributes of the respondent did not show a significant association with LET performance. However, high school and college academic performance were noted to have significant and highly significant associations with LET performance in General Education Courses. High school academic performance had a Chi-square value of 19.234 and a statistical significance of 0.004, while, college academic performance had a Chi-square value of 16.356 and a statistical significance value of 0.003.

It can then be deduced from the previous findings that LET performance is likely to be associated with the academic performances of the respondents in high school and college. This means that as students get better performance in high school and college general weighted average, they are less likely not to pass the LET exam. This is congruent with the study of Pachejo *et al.*, (2013), which revealed that students' academic grades are predictors of their performance in the board examination. Their study showed that when the board exam is correlated with the three components of the academic subjects, there is a moderate correlation with general education. In contrast, the correlation between professional education and specialization indicates a slight correlation.

In addition, Dagdag *et al.*, (2017) found that low academic performance influences low LET performance. Moreover, according to several types of research, college academic performance affects licensure examination performance. Academic performance is a good predictor of LET performance. The graduate low college general weighted averages (GWA) are closely associated with their low LET scores. Hence, students with high academic achievement are likely to achieve high in LET. Consequently, it is of importance that teachers ascertain their students are performing high in their academic courses.

Table 4. Correlation between Demographics and Licensure Examination Performance

(I) Demographics	(J) LET Performance	(I-J) X ² -value	Sig
Sex	General Education	3.920	0.270
	Specialization	3.998	0.135
	Professional Education	5.688	0.058
Age	General Education	5.706	0.457
	Specialization	3.252	0.517
	Professional Education	1.339	0.855
Civil Status	General Education	2.434	0.487
	Specialization	1.167	0.558
	Professional Education	1.676	0.433
Family Income	General Education	11.108	0.745
	Specialization	7.821	0.646
	Professional Education	8.844	0.547
High School Academic Performance (GA)	General Education	19.234**	0.004
	Specialization	9.430	0.051
	Professional Education	7.292	0.094

College Entrance Test (CET) Results	General Education	16.529	0.168
	Specialization	9.464	0.305
	Professional Education	15.241	0.055
College Academic Performance (GWA)	General Education	9.827	0.132
	Specialization	16.356**	0.003
	Professional Education	11.89*	0.018
Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Factors Licensure Examination Performance: Pearson’s Product Moment of Correlation tests was carried out to examine which factors significantly influenced LET performance. Five factors were identified: personal, teacher, school, family, and review preparations. Of them, only the personal factors had a statistically significant correlation—the remaining all registered p-values greater than .05 which implies a non-significant correlation between variables.

The statistical significance between the personal factors and the student's performance in the three areas: General Education, Specialization, and Professional Education, were indicated by their calculated r-values of 0.179, 0.238, and 0.183, respectively. Their registered p-values were 0.047, 0.008, 0.042. It can then be drawn from these results that the influence of personal factors on their performance cannot just be by chance. Personal factors had likely improved them in those areas. Additionally, as they exert more personal efforts, they would have more chance of increasing their performance. Hence, interest, motivation, and study habits would have a great impact on the performance of graduates on the Licensure Examinations.

Table 5. Factors correlated with Licensure Examination Performance

(I) Factors	(J) Performance	(I-J) r-value	p-value
Personal	General Education	0.179*	0.047
	Specialization	0.238**	0.008
	Professional Education	0.183*	0.042
Teacher	General Education	0.124	0.171
	Specialization	0.124	0.172
	Professional Education	0.108	0.233
School	General Education	0.084	0.355
	Specialization	0.090	0.321
	Professional Education	0.105	0.246
Family	General Education	0.094	0.299
	Specialization	0.139	0.125
	Professional Education	0.127	0.161
Review Preparations	General Education	0.052	0.571
	Specialization	0.116	0.200
	Professional Education	0.050	0.586
Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

These findings are corroborated by the Self-efficacy Theory of Bandura (2006) which refers to an individual's belief in his or her capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance attainments. Self-efficacy reflects confidence in the ability to exert control over one's own motivation, behavior, and social environment. These cognitive self-evaluations influence all manner of human experience, including the goals for which people strive, the amount of energy expended toward goal achievement, and the likelihood of attaining particular levels of behavioral performance. This theory assisted in understanding the nature of the respondents’ personal preparation and their success for licensure examination.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- ✓ Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Biological Science graduates of are academically prepared for the examination as indicated their given demographic and academic characteristics;
- ✓ The students performed best in general education than in professional education and major courses; their LET performance are significantly associated with their high school and college academic standing, and are positively and significantly influenced by some personal factors.

From the preceding conclusions, the following were the recommendations:

- ✓ Regularly revisit and strictly implement the admission and retention policies;
- ✓ Impose and institutionalize the qualifying grades and examinations to students who will be admitted to the program;
- ✓ Utilize standardized test questions for entrance test and qualifying examinations;
- ✓ Internalize the knowledge, concepts, principles, and skills students may learn in the basic, professional education and specialization subjects; and
- ✓ Provide students enough preparation for examination, intensify the conduct of the comprehensive reviews and adopt a stringent policy on attendance and participation of the students during the review.

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Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest of any kind.

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